

REFORMING BITS AND INVESTOR-STATE DISPUTE SETTLEMENT IN CENTRAL ASIA

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Abstract. *This dissertation examines the challenges of drafting substantive provisions of a Model Bilateral Investment Treaty (BIT) for Central Asia and integration of reformed Investor-State Dispute Settlement (ISDS) mechanisms. It analyzes existing BITs, global reform and regional practices and national legislation on foreign investments in Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan. Using comparative and doctrinal methods, the study proposes a balanced framework emphasizing the balance between the investor protection and the right of states to regulate. The research contributes to developing a coherent regional Model BIT that aligns foreign investment protection with sustainable development goals.*

Key words. *Bilateral Investment Treaty (BIT), Investor-State Dispute Settlement (ISDS), Central Asia, investment treaty reform, Model BIT, sustainable development, investor obligations, dispute avoidance.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu dissertatsiya O'rta Osiyo uchun namunaviy ikkitomonlama investitsiya shartnomasining asosiy qoidalarini ishlab chiqish va isloh qilingan investor-davlat nizolarini hal qilish mexanizmlarini integratsiyalash muammolarini o'rganadi. Unda Qozog'iston, O'zbekiston, Qirg'iziston, Tojikiston va Turkmanistondagi mavjud ikkitomonlama global islohotlar, mintaqaviy amaliyotlar, va xorijiy investitsiyalar to'g'risidagi milliy qonunchilik tahlil qilingan. Qiyosiy va doktrinal usullardan foydalangan holda, tadqiqot investorlarni himoya qilish va davlatlarning tartibga solish huquqi o'rtasidagi muvozanatni ta'kidlaydigan muvozanatli tuzilmani taklif etadi. Tadqiqot xorijiy investitsiyalarni himoya qilishni*

barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlariga muvofiqlashtiradigan izchil mintaqaviy ikkitomonlama investitsiya shartnomasi namunasini ishlab chiqishga hissa qo'shadi.

Tayanch so'zlar. *Ikki tomonlama investitsiya shartnomasi, investor-davlat nizolarini hal qilish, O'rta Osiyo, investitsiya shartnomalarini isloh qilish, ikkitomonlama investitsiya shartnomasi namunasi, barqaror rivojlanish, investor majburiyatlari, nizolarning oldini olish.*

Introduction. The proliferation of international investment agreements (IIA) since the 1990s has fundamentally reshaped economic governance, foreign direct investment (FDI) activity, and resolution of disputes. In this regard, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan (Central Asia), after gaining their independence, actively participated in the process of concluding bilateral investment agreements to attract foreign capital needed for post-transition economic development.¹ The agreements on investments concluded during this period, however, were based on the model of capital-exporting countries and, consequently, provided more favourable conditions and terms for the protection of investors' interests rather than the states, prioritized investors' rights over the right of state to regulate, and sustainable development. Expansive provisions on standards of treatment, including fair and equitable treatment, full protection and security, national and most-favoured nation treatment, as well as direct access to international arbitration as means of resolving disputes did not strike the right balance between the interests of investors and the states.

Despite the above, Central Asia is increasingly attracting FDI and not only from the Western countries.² As the economies of these countries grow so does the need to

¹ This pattern is illustrated by Uzbekistan, which began concluding investment treaties in 1992, shortly after gaining its independence, and adopted a series of bilateral investment treaties throughout the 1990s and early 2000s to signal its openness to foreign investment. OECD Roadmap for Sustainable Investment Policy Reforms in Uzbekistan, 2025 - pp.163-165. Available at: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2025/11/roadmap-for-sustainable-investment-policy-reforms-in-uzbekistan_68204584.html

² The Report of the Eurasian Development Bank on Monitoring of Mutual Investments. Available at: <https://eabr.org/en/press/news/investment-inflows-into-the-urasian-region-from-asian-countries-in-2024-2025->

reform the current regulatory framework for foreign investments. In this regard, a Model Bilateral Investment Treaty (Model BIT) for Central Asia, which would provide for regulation of FDI and take into account strengths and weaknesses of the economies and political regime of Central Asia, would serve as a guiding framework for Central Asian countries to negotiate future treaties with investors and other states and renegotiate the existing ones. It is also of paramount importance that a Model BIT encompasses a reformed investor-state dispute settlement (ISDS) mechanism regulation of which also poses significant drafting challenges for these countries given the domestic legislation of the countries on FDIs and ISDS.

Given the breadth the topic can explore, this dissertation has intentionally been subjected to the following qualifications. First, it addresses only those aspects of bilateral investment treaties that pertain to private international law, in particular the notion of investor, and investments, treatment and protection of foreign investors and investor-state dispute settlement, and inclusion of investor obligations whereas questions regulated by BITs that belong to public international law, such as inter-state obligations and state-to-State dispute settlement, fall outside its scope. Second, as regards model instruments, the study examines only model BITs adopted after 2015, which reflect the new generation of treaty practice. Third, the analysis of investment disputes is confined to cases connected to Central Asia. Fourth, in respect of domestic law, the study considers the principal foreign-investment laws of the Central Asian States and policy recommendations developed by international organizations.³ Fifth, the

[amounted-to-us-20-bill/](https://gov.uz/en/miit/news/view/116876) According to the report, the volume of FDI from Asian countries alone into Central Asia accounted for 68 billion USD in the first half of 2025, and the main recipients of investments were Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan. According to the Ministry of Investments, Industry and Trade of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 2025, the total volume of investments implemented in Uzbekistan alone reached 43,1 billion USD. <https://gov.uz/en/miit/news/view/116876>

³ UNCTAD Report on the Implementation of the Investment Policy Review: Uzbekistan, 2021. Available at: <https://unctad.org/publication/report-implementation-investment-policy-review-uzbekistan>. UNCTAD Report on the Implementation of the Investment Policy Review: Tajikistan, 2023. Available at: <https://unctad.org/publication/report-implementation-investment-policy-review-tajikistan>. OECD, Building a Competitive Investment Landscape in Turkmenistan, 2025. Available at:

geographic scope is limited to the five Central Asian republics, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan. Moreover, the study relies on publicly available treaty and case materials, in particular the UNCTAD Investment Policy Hub.

The architecture of IIAs. Talking about the statistics, at the time of writing as of June 16 June 2026, the UNCTAD Investment Policy Hub lists a total of 2,864 bilateral investment treaties (BITs) worldwide, of which 2237 are currently in force.⁴ With respect to the treaty practice of Central Asia, as of June 2026, 231 BITs involving Central Asian states are recorded in the UNCTAD Investment Policy Hub, with 175 being in force: Kyrgyzstan has concluded 40 BITs, with 27 being in force, Kazakhstan 56, with 45 being in force, Uzbekistan 59, with 50 being in force, Turkmenistan 31, with 25 being in force, Tajikistan 45, with 28 being in force.⁵ These treaties constitute the primary legal framework governing the protection of foreign investors and investments in the region.⁶ In addition, UNCTAD identifies 96 Model BITs adopted by states, 17 of which have been replaced since their initial adoption.⁷ According to UNCTAD data and the national legal databases of Central Asian states, none of the Central Asian countries has a Model BIT which is publicly available.

The BITs of Central Asia. The development of regulation of FDI through BITs in Central Asia happened in stages. Despite the fact that several of more recent BITs signed by Central Asian countries take into account sustainable development goals,

https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2025/11/building-a-competitive-investment-landscape-in-turkmenistan_36d9ccc5.html and others

⁴ UNCTAD Investment Policy Hub, International Investment Agreements Navigator. Available at: <https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/international-investment-agreements>.

⁵ UNCTAD Investment Policy Hub, International Investment Agreements Navigator. Available at: <https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/international-investment-agreements>.

⁶ The practical stakes of this framework are heightened in economies where the foreign-investment footprint is large. In Turkmenistan, for instance, FDI stock relative to GDP has run some 20 to 30 percentage points above the regional average, placing it, together with Kazakhstan, among the region's leaders in inward FDI stock. OECD, Building a Competitive Investment Landscape in Turkmenistan, 2025 – ch.1. Available at: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2025/11/building-a-competitive-investment-landscape-in-turkmenistan_36d9ccc5.html

⁷ UNCTAD Investment Policy Hub, International Investment Agreements Navigator, Model Agreements at the link: <https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/international-investment-agreements/model-agreements>.

regional integration frameworks, balance of investor protection and the right of state to regulate, albeit in a fragmentary manner,⁸ the vast majority of these instruments were negotiated during the 1990s and early 2000s, during a period when these states lacked experienced treaty negotiators and operated under significant pressure to demonstrate openness to foreign investment. As stated rightly by J.Maupin that “...transparency has made significant inroads into the treaty negotiating process in [only] recent years, and... this gave rise to a new generation of ‘model BITs’ whose proposed contents are routinely disclosed in advance by the responsible government agencies and then revised in response to extensive public comment and legislative review processes”.⁹ As stated by R.Ecandi, newly negotiated international investment agreements (IIA) are detailed, comprehensive, rigorous, and based on the accumulated experience of investor-state dispute settlement.¹⁰

Nonetheless, most Central Asian BITs contain no provisions on investor obligations, anti-corruption duties, or sustainability standards, creating a significant imbalance between rights and responsibilities.¹¹ The substantive standards contained in Central Asian BITs reflect the generic formulations common to first-generation treaties. Fair and equitable treatment provisions are typically formulated without any qualifications or inclusions of its elements, leaving arbitral tribunals with broad

⁸ For example, the 2020 Hungary-Kyrgyzstan BIT, the 2024 India-Uzbekistan BIT, the 2025 Jordan-Uzbekistan BIT and others. Available by search at Electronic Database of Investment Treaties: <https://edit.wti.org/document/investment-treaty/search>

⁹ Julie A. Maupin. Transparency in International Investment Law: The Good, the Bad, and the Murky, in Transparency in International Law - pp. 142-171. Andrea Bianchi & Anne Peters eds., Cambridge University Press, 2013 - p.8. Available at: https://scholarship.law.duke.edu/faculty_scholarship/3126/

¹⁰ Roberto Echandi. Bilateral investment treaties and investment provisions in preferential trade agreements. Recent developments in investment rule-making - pp. 3-30. Yannaca-Small, Katia ed., Arbitration Under International Investment Agreements: A Guide to the Key Issues, Oxford University Press, 2nd Edition, 2018 - p. 9

¹¹ UNCTAD has observed that such first-generation treaties may contain broadly drafted provisions exposing the host State to claims before investment tribunals and lack sustainable development-oriented features, and that their content needs to be modernised. UNCTAD Report on the Implementation of the Investment Policy Review: Uzbekistan, 2021 - p.9. Available at: <https://unctad.org/publication/report-implementation-investment-policy-review-uzbekistan> UNCTAD Report on the Implementation of the Investment Policy Review: Tajikistan, 2023, - p.11. Available at: <https://unctad.org/publication/report-implementation-investment-policy-review-tajikistan>

interpretive discretion to impose expansive obligations. Most-favoured-nation (MFN) clauses in many Central Asian BITs lack carve-outs for preferential arrangements concluded within regional frameworks. Expropriation provisions in many treaties fail to distinguish adequately between direct expropriation and regulatory measures taken in the public interest, a distinction that has proved critical in arbitral practice.¹²

This development has had consequences of its own. At the time of writing, Central Asian states are known to be respondents in 70 disputes commenced under various investment treaties.¹³ Statistical analysis of investment arbitration data reveals that Central Asian states lose or settle a disproportionately high share of the cases brought against them, in part due to the breadth of substantive obligations assumed under existing BITs.¹⁴ The financial exposure associated from with adverse awards can also be substantial. For example, in *Rumeli v. Kazakhstan* case, which was decided in favor of the investor, the arbitral tribunal awarded the amount of compensation equal to 125 mln USD.¹⁵ This illustrates the fiscal risk that investment arbitration may pose to the public purse in the region.

The necessity of reform. The most direct avenue for reform is the renegotiation or termination of existing BITs and their replacement with modern instruments reflecting current international standards. In this context, a model BIT would establish a framework to guide future reforms. The key issue in developing a Model BIT for Central Asia include striking the right balance between investor protection and the right of the

¹² On the distinction between indirect expropriation and non-discriminatory regulatory measures adopted in the public interest, see Dolzer, Kriebaum and Schreuer, *Principles of International Investment Law*. Oxford University Press, 3rd Edition, 2022 - pp. 153–171.

¹³ UNCTAD Investment Policy Hub, Investment Dispute Settlement Navigator at: <https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/investment-dispute-settlement/>

¹⁴ The link between old-generation instruments and exposure to arbitration is illustrated by Uzbekistan, where all of the ICSID and UNCITRAL proceedings brought against the State invoked the previous investment law and/or an old-generation BIT as the basis of arbitration. UNCTAD Report on the Implementation of the Investment Policy Review: Uzbekistan, 2021- p. 39. Available at: <https://unctad.org/publication/report-implementation-investment-policy-review-uzbekistan>

¹⁵ *Rumeli v. Kazakhstan*. Summary of the case details available at: <https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/investment-dispute-settlement/cases/185/rumeli-v-kazakhstan>

state to regulate. This master dissertation analyzes the current investment regulatory framework, the ISDS history of Central Asian states, and global reform initiatives promoted by international institutions and proposes reform agendas. In particular, the UNCTAD Investment Policy Framework for Sustainable Development (IPFSD)¹⁶ provides a valuable reference point for reforming Central Asian BITs and the author of the master dissertation considers its recommendations in proposing a Model BIT wording. The IPFSD advocates a new generation of investment treaties that balance investment protection with the preservation of host-state regulatory space, incorporate sustainable development objectives, and establish clear investor obligations alongside investor rights. Applying the IPFSD framework to the Central Asian context would involve, inter alia, replacing open-ended FET clauses with exhaustive lists of specific obligations, narrowing the definition of covered investment to exclude speculative financial instruments, and inserting general exceptions specific to economies of these countries and their regional participation in economic cooperations.¹⁷ This master dissertation also considers UNCITRAL Working Group III proposals and the implementation of ISDS reform options in the context of Central Asia.

Conclusion. The reform of bilateral investment treaties and investor-state dispute settlement in Central Asia is both urgent and achievable. The existing treaty regime, shaped by first-generation BITs concluded under conditions of asymmetric bargaining power and limited legal expertise, imposes disproportionate constraints on the regulatory autonomy of Central Asian states without delivering commensurate benefits

¹⁶ UNCTAD Investment Policy Hub, Investment Policy Framework for Sustainable Development. Available at: <https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/investment-policy-framework>

¹⁷ The development imperative underlying this reform agenda is illustrated by Turkmenistan, whose foreign investment remains overwhelmingly concentrated in the extractive sector, with gas-industry projects accounting for some 98,7% of the FDI planned for 2025 and little inflow reaching non-resource tradable sectors. The authorities aim to attract greater levels of FDI outside the hydrocarbon sector as a foundation for long-term and sustainable growth, an objective that a modern, development-oriented treaty framework would support. OECD, Building a Competitive Investment Landscape in Turkmenistan, 2025 - chs. 1 and 3. Available at: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2025/11/building-a-competitive-investment-landscape-in-turkmenistan_36d9ccc5.html

in terms of investment promotion or legal certainty. The wing exposure of these states to costly and unpredictable investment arbitration proceedings reinforces the case for comprehensive reform.

This thesis argues that effective reform in the Central Asian context must proceed along two interconnected dimensions. First, substantive treaty standards must be modernised to reflect the balanced approach, preserving adequate investment protection while safeguarding the right to regulate in the public interest. ISDS mechanisms should be reformed for greater legitimacy and consistency, following UNCITRAL Working Group III's recommendations.

The reform agenda outlined in this thesis is also consistent with, and reinforced by, broader global trends toward a more sustainable and balanced international investment law. Central Asia's strategic location at the crossroads of major transcontinental economic corridors and its significance as a destination for investment from both East and West lends particular importance to the development of a robust, legitimate, and development-oriented investment treaty regime in the region.

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